

WORDS OF POSITIVE WISHES OF THE UZBEK AND KARAKALPAK PEOPLES AROUND THE TABLE

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Abstract: The examination of praise and wishes of the Uzbek and Karakalpak peoples around the table is the center of this article. This procedure is frequently used to communicate positive wishes during celebrations and festivities.

Keywords: *applause, positive desire, prayer, wish, speech etiquette, food, household applause, food, happy life, aging.*

Applause and wishes are utilized in folklore in various forms and meanings in everyday life. Everyday applause has no unique creators or performers. Wherever they are needed, older people speak them. There are three forms of clapping: applause at the meeting, applause at the table, and applause at the start of a business or event. Each of these three species has its own distinct traits. Due to different circumstances, the lexicon of ceremonial names is genetically generated directly on the basis of that people's linguistic richness, sometimes by gaining terms from the lexical richness of other, typically surrounding ethnic groupings. The emergence of new ethnographic phenomena in the subsequent historical process of ethnos life is also a factor that ensures the continuous development of ceremonial lexicon.

People who live next to one other constantly influence, borrow, and integrate

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each other's ideas. This is frequently visible in the set of words used to describe the ritual. As a result, in some instances, the influx of vocabulary units expressing rituals from other people's languages is also one of the causes of ceremonial lexicon enrichment.

Folklorists' research into the scope, location, and content of the words acclaim and desire in folklore, in our opinion, needs more precise additions.

A lot of social elements are linked to the creation of desire and applause units. The Uzbek people's traditions, rites, beliefs, and national ideals are among them. It appears that, in addition to researching the lexical and grammatical characteristics of Uzbek applauding units, they must also be classified according to their content and speech.

The lexical richness of any language is known to be researched in the linguistics department's lexicology department, which analyzes the structural and systemic elements of lexical richness, as well as the rules of their growth and their relationship with other branches of language (phonetics and grammar).

Lexicology also considers the processes of obsolescence and renewal of a language's vocabulary, the role of linguistic and extralinguistic elements, the functional-semantic description of existing lexical units, old, new lexical layers, and linguistic theme groups.

When the lexical features of each language are studied on various levels, such as the laws of language development, language and thinking, the influence of language and society relations on the lexical structure, lexical units in terms of modernity, history, expressive-stylistic the definition of socio-philological processes, such as the division into different thematic layers, lexical units in terms of modernity, history, expressive-stylistic the definition of socio-philological processes, such as the division into different.

People wishing each other well is one of the most popular expressions in the Uzbek and Karakalpak cultures of communication. Praying, cheering, wishing,

and wishing well are examples of such statements. However, the term applause is suitable in the above-mentioned research of Uzbek folk oral poetry. In addition to applause, such units include prayer phrases, phrases such as "*Let the house be full of wheat,*" "*Find blessings,*" and some proverbs and phrases.

Positive desire units have been used in our people's history from ancient times, and instances can be found in prayers, ceremonial etiquette, phrases, and proverbs.

The happy wishes around the table are various due to the hospitality of the Uzbek and Karakalpak people.

When Uzbek and Karakalpak families visit a house, the table is set with the following words: "May this room is filled with peace and quiet." May the homeowners live long and see their children's wishes come true! The following positive wishes in the form of text are used when setting the table, eating and after the meal: "*Let there be no state, let there be generosity, let there be endless pleasure, let there be no prosperity in your house, let there be happiness in your house, let there be plenty of tablecloths, let there be a face in front of your neighbors May your light be long, may your tongue be long, may your destiny be full, may your intentions be great, may your table be full, may your food be whole!*"

The following prayer is recited around the table: "*Let us not lose our seats. May the blessings of what we eat and drink touch those who pass by here! May our work come from the right, may our destiny be formed!*"

The most commonly used phrases are "*Let the one who gives soup, let the state that does not go, let the state give a broad verb! Blessings, the state increases*".

The above instances demonstrate that, according to our people's customs, entering a house is a beautiful gesture to the owners, and then when the table is set, those seated around it desire the human health and wellbeing, longevity,

success, wealth, harmony, and well-being in the future. Even when the guest is not present, each apartment owner with a table setup and before the table is washed, himself, family members, and relatives wants applause reflecting similar happy wishes for his connections. The topic of responses and speech propriety reflects the applause heard.

The word **pray** is often used in the context of applause, followed by sentences expressing a positive desire, such as *"Let our prayers be accepted, and enjoy the seven rewards of the prayers we recite."*

The word duo in the Uzbek language has been used for a long time. Units ending "**Olohu Akbar**" in (Allah is great, Allah is great) were used.

The Arabic lexeme duo was adopted in both Persian and Turkish, and is one of the most widely used words in Islam, being used in the language of ancient Uzbek written records from the 14th to the 15th centuries. In the language of "Muhabbatnoma" (Khorezmi's work) and in the works of AlisherNavoi in the 15th century, it became a polysemous word in both poetic and prose works:

- "Pray"** - 1. Ambitions; pray to god for good.
 2. purpose, demand, desire.
 3. Wishing you a long life.
 4. Amurlet.

The Persian word for prayer is duo: the phrase "**pray for goods**" is a prayer for good deeds; "**Prayer of the soul**" is a prayer for someone's life and well-being, and always means "**your prayer is in your soul.**"

The word duo is also formed in compound verbs: to pray, to pray, to pray. The Arabic grammatical form of the word pray is also found in the language of written monuments in Uzbek.

Examples of written texts that show the different meanings of the word duo in a sentence: Golden apple, take a prayer, isn't a prayer a gold? (Proverbs).

"Father, I don't need your money, just pray," he said hurriedly. (S.Ahmad)

After the prayer, Otabek took out a blanket and held it in a box. (A.Qodiriy) The prayer of many will be a lake (Proverb) Say a prayer to my aunt, my daughter ... - said Aunt Tokhta (I. Rahim).

The word tandem appeared in the examples above as a syllable of appreciation with several definitions.

As a result of the foregoing, it can be stated that positive desire content units have a wide range of content and are classified into several content groups. They possess peace, harmony, health, longevity, a pleasant life, good luck, sustenance, congrats on holy days, a large family, money, and strength in particular. The applause's content will be represented as a joyful existence with twofold aging.

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